

DiSSCo Transition Project

DiSSCo DMP ready for use in the ERIC

Work Package 3 - Deliverable 3.3

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Executive Summary

This deliverable updates and enhances the DiSSCo Data Management Plan (DMP) by revising the provisional DMP for the DiSSCo infrastructure in light of the latest developments and integrating machine-actionable functionalities in alignment with the Research Data Alliance (RDA) DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs. This transformation enables automated data exchange, improved interoperability, and better alignment with FAIR principles.

The provisional DiSSCO DMP has been transferred to GitHub, ensuring efficient version control, accessibility, and transparency. Additionally, an example implementation of the machine-actionable DMP for the DISSCO infrastructure has been developed for components that conform to the machine-actionable DMP standard. To achieve this, several features and functionalities have been introduced to enhance integration with other repositories and Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), as well as to develop a user-friendly and intuitive interface for creating and managing DMPs. The updated DMP incorporates metadata retrieval, dataset tracking, structured dataset descriptions, and compliance validation.

Challenges (e.g., ensuring continuous updates and user adoption) and future developments (such as evaluating the completeness and FAIRness of the DMP) have also been outlined.

By incorporating machine-actionability into DiSSCo's DMP improves overall efficiency and quality of data management, enhances interoperability, increases research visibility, and supports sustainable, standardised data-sharing practices.

Keywords

DiSSCo, data management plan, machine-actionable, data infrastructure, FAIR, natural history collections, open data

List of abbreviations

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DMP - Data Management Plan

DO - Digital Object

DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project

FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

maDMP - machine-actionable Data Management Plan

RDA - Research Data Alliance

RI - Research Infrastructure

RO - Research Output

SKG - Scientific Knowledge Graph

List of tables

Table 1 - List of datasets and services described in the DiSSCo machine-actionable DMP (page 12)

1. Introduction

The purpose of Task 3.3 and this deliverable is to update the provisional DiSSCo Data Management Plan (DMP), which was initiated during the ICEDIG project (Hardisty, 2019), and make it machine-actionable in accordance with the Research Data Alliance (RDA) DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable Data Management Plans (Miksa et al., 2020). While traditional Data Management Plans are often free-form text documents describing the data used and produced during a research project – such as where the data can be accessed, how it is archived, which licences apply, and to whom credit should be given – machine-actionable DMPs, adhering to the common standard and application profile, enable the automatic exchange, integration, and validation of information contained within DMPs. Thus, it facilitates the exchange of information between systems acting on behalf of stakeholders involved in the research life cycle, such as researchers, funders, repository managers, and others.

The Plan-Track-Assess framework (Reichmann et al., 2024), proposed by the OSTRails project¹ provides a high-level, tool-independent framework that outlines how researchers, research managers, and funders plan, track, and assess the management of digital objects (DO)² in their DMP in alignment with the FAIR principles. The “Plan” component of the framework, along with its proposed pathway, outlines how researchers develop DMPs, retrieve metadata, and assess these plans to improve their adherence to FAIR principles.

Based on user stories from multiple scientific disciplines, Reichmann et al. identified user actions that occur while creating DMPs via a DMP platform. These actions can trigger interactions with other components, such as searching and retrieving metadata for research outputs and digital objects via repositories or Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), adding a DMP to a repository, and evaluating the completeness and FAIRness of a DMP and/or the research output listed within it.

As recommendations, they outline the following needs for the “Plan” pathway:

- 1) **Enhance integration** of DMP platforms with SKGs and repositories by enabling seamless searches for research outputs and digital objects via SKGs and efficient retrieval of metadata.
- 2) **Expand DMP platform capabilities** to not only create and store DMPs but also evaluate the completeness and FAIRness of DMPs and associated research outputs.
- 3) **Develop user-friendly and intuitive interfaces** to guide researchers through the processes of creating, managing, and evaluating DMPs.

In this task, we aim to align the provisional DiSSCo DMP with the framework proposed by the OSTRails project by making parts of the traditional DiSSCo DMP machine-actionable in accordance with the RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable Data management Plans³. Additionally, we introduce elements for integration with other repositories and SKGs, alongside with a user-friendly interface to manage the DMP and its associated datasets and services.

2. Update to the provisional DiSSCo DMP

¹ <https://ostrails.eu/>

² A record (e.g. dataset, publication, software, etc.) identified with persistent identifier and described by metadata.

³ <https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard>

The DiSSCo DMP, initially published during the ICEDIG project (D6.6) and later supplemented by the DiSSCo Prepare (D6.4; Weiland et al., 2024) projects, has been revised to reflect the current status of the DiSSCo project at the time of this deliverable. To improve accessibility, facilitate management, and track updates and changes, the provisional DMP was revised and moved to GitHub⁴ for ongoing updates. This enables efficient version control and ease of use.

- **Unaccommodated Components:** Any elements of the DMP that could not be integrated into the RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs were updated and retained in the GitHub version.
- **Accommodated Components:** All components that conform to the machine-actionable DMP standard are referenced from the GitHub version, ensuring both compliance and traceability.

3. Implementation of the RDA DMP Common Standard on PlutoF platform

The RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs (maDMP) is a metadata application profile designed to provide basic interoperability between systems producing or consuming machine-actionable data management plans. It is intended to cover a wide range of use cases and represents information throughout the entire DMP lifecycle. The standard includes nested modules and terms to describe the DMP, its related costs, contributors, linked projects and their funding, as well as planned, produced, and published datasets (including services and resources) with accompanying metadata and distribution information.

As stated by Miksa et al. (2019), the machine-actionability of the DMP allows parts of it to be automatically generated and shared, reducing administrative workload and improving the quality of information within the DMP. For example, data repositories could consume information about new datasets, including the data type and volume indicated in the maDMP. A data repository operator could then receive a notification with the estimated storage costs to reserve space for a future data deposit. The maDMP could also benefit researchers and funders by enabling them to track progress, such as monitoring the use of published datasets through citation statistics retrieved from external services like OpenCitations⁵, and by generating automated, scalable, on demand reports over time. In response to user-initiated actions, it can retrieve metadata and statistics, including citations, for specific datasets (e.g., those published in Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)⁶ or DataCite⁷, or scientific articles published in journals).

PlutoF⁸ is an open data management platform designed to handle diverse biodiversity data types, fully linked and ready for analysis. The platform supports the entire data lifecycle — from creating Data Management Plans to uploading, publishing, and archiving datasets — in a FAIR manner.

⁴ https://github.com/TU-NHM/DiSSCo_DMP

⁵ <https://opencitations.net>

⁶ <https://www.gbif.org/>

⁷ <https://datacite.org/>

⁸ <https://plutof.ut.ee>

As part of this deliverable, we implemented the RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs into PlutoF, enabling users to describe project-related datasets, resources, and tools, whether in preliminary or final states. Furthermore, we attempted to incorporate components of the DiSSCo DMP into the PlutoF implementation of the RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs. To better align with the Plan-Track-Assess framework proposed by the OStrails project, we introduced features that address recommendations for enhancing integration with other repositories and SKGs, as well as developing user-friendly and intuitive interfaces for creating and managing DMPs -

- **Collaborative Features:** In addition to a graphical user interface for the RDA DMP Common Standard data model, PlutoF allows registered users to work collaboratively in a group setting to complete the DMP (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Screenshot of the PlutoF platform demonstrating the access rights options for managing the DMP record.

- **ORCID Integration:** PlutoF supports registration and login using ORCID sign-in, facilitating seamless user authentication and integration with other research platforms (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Screenshot of the PlutoF platform sign-in options.

- **Dataset Metadata Pre-fill:** A Digital Object (DO) can be linked to the DMP, with dataset metadata pre-filled by using external services (such as the DataCite API⁹) to retrieve the DO metadata (Figure 3).

⁹ <https://support.datacite.org/reference/introduction>

Figure 3. Screenshot of the PlutoF platform demonstrating the dataset metadata pre-fill functionality.

- **Dataset Citation Statistics:** Citation statistics for each dataset associated with the DMP are retrieved from the OpenCitations API¹⁰ and displayed (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Screenshot of the PlutoF platform displaying dataset citation statistics for all datasets with DOIs linked to the DMP.

- **Publishing DMP via DataCite:** PlutoF enables the direct publishing of datasets through DataCite, and the process of publishing a DMP via DataCite has been streamlined to require just a single mouse-click to initiate (Figure 5). New versions of the same DMP will be published under the same DOI by versioning the JSON-formatted DMP within the associated media of the DOI record.

¹⁰ <https://opencitations.net/api>

Figure 5. Screenshot of the PlutoF platform demonstrating the direct publishing of a DMP via DataCite.

For future development, we have planned functionality for evaluating the completeness and FAIRness of the DMP and/or the research outputs listed within it.

3.1. Examples of resource types applicable to machine-actionable DMPs

The RDA Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs accepts dataset and resource types based on the DataCite metadata schema¹¹. These include Collection, Dataset, Model, Service, Software, and Workflow, among others. The types of data DiSSCo handles, will be collected from various sources, including publicly available datasets, institutional or private data, as well as self-generated data. In the machine-actionable DMP, we included: 1) data shared or generated through the DiSSCo infrastructure, and 2) e-services developed under or provided by the DiSSCo infrastructure. These are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of datasets and services described in the DiSSCo machine-actionable DMP (partially adapted from Koureas et al. (2024), Table 1). The full list of datasets and services, along with information about formats, standards, and references, is available in the DiSSCo DMP's GitHub repository (Tables 1 and 2).

Title	Type
DiSSCover (Unified Curation & Annotation System)	Service or Interactive resource
ELViS (European Loans and Visits System)	Service or Interactive resource
CDD (Collection Digitisation Dashboard)	Service or Interactive resource

¹¹ https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.1/doc/DataCite-MetadataKernel_v4.1.pdf

Digital Specimen Repository	Service or Interactive resource
Knowledgebase	Service or Interactive resource
Digital Collection Data	Dataset/Compiled data
Digital Specimen data	Dataset/Compiled data
Links to Digital Media (and other extended data)	Dataset/Compiled data
Annotations	Dataset/Compiled data
Provenance data	Dataset/Compiled data
Method and protocol descriptions	Text/Research protocol
Infrastructure and operational data (logs, error reports)	Text/Log or Text/Error report
User authentication and authorization records	Text
DiSSCo agreed vocabularies and ontologies	Text
Technical documentation on standards developed by DiSSCo	Text
Transactions (loans, visits, access requests, queries)	Dataset/Compiled data
Website data	Interactive resource/Website
Literature (scientific papers, posters)	Text/Journal article or Text/Conference poster or Text/Conference paper or Text/Report
Dissemination and communication materials	Text/Blog post
Training materials	Learning object

3.2. Version control and updates to machine-actionable DMPs

There are multiple options for publishing maDMPs. One option is to publish different versions of the maDMP in JSON format via DataCite, where both previous and new versions can be tracked using appropriate terms for the related identifier's relation type (*IsPreviousVersionOf*, *IsNewVersionOf*) in the DataCite Metadata Schema. An alternative option is to publish updated JSON-formatted versions of the same DMP under the same DOI by linking new associated media to the existing DOI record. Additionally, updated versions of the maDMP in JSON format could be included in the GitHub repository for the traditional DMP.

Updates to the DMP can be made either quarterly or biannually, in line with the project reporting periods when information on contributions, dissemination, and research outputs is collected from project partners. The task of maintaining and updating the DMP could be integrated into ongoing project activities, with changes communicated to stakeholders through automated notifications from GitHub. By using GitHub issue reporting and pull requests, users can provide feedback on the DMP or suggest improvements.

3.3. Generating reports from machine-actionable DMPs

maDMPs stored in PlutoF can be viewed within PlutoF, downloaded as JSON-formatted files, or queried using the DMP identifier via the PlutoF API¹². maDMPs published in DataCite can be retrieved using the DataCite REST API¹³.

On public platforms (e.g., the DiSSCo web portal), the maDMP could be integrated with more advanced analytics and visualisations for reporting purposes.

Several examples of the JSON output of the DiSSCo maDMP datasets and services are available at the DiSSCo DMP GitHub repository.

4. Discussion

In the current task, we identified potential challenges in making DMPs machine-actionable:

1. **Ongoing updates and version control:** Who will be continuously updating and republishing the DMP and maDMP components? Proper version control needs to be ensured, as maDMPs should ideally be updated throughout the research lifecycle. Additionally, tracking changes and maintaining transparency across multiple collaborators can be challenging.
2. **User adoption and administrative burden:** Compared to traditional DMPs, the added complexity and potential user resistance to adopting new workflows may increase the administrative burden, particularly if systems are not user-friendly and there are no resources for training.
3. **Lack of incentives:** Researchers do not currently see tangible rewards for adopting and maintaining maDMPs.
4. **Technical limitations:** While the RDA DMP Common Standards Working Group has developed a standardised format and data standard, technical challenges remain, including:
 - a. Insufficient infrastructure to support real-time updates and dynamic content in maDMPs.
 - b. Issues with data synchronisation between multiple systems.
 - c. Scalability and customisation challenges, particularly in large-scale or collaborative projects where discipline-specific customisation may be required.
 - d. Lack of long-term support and maintenance for essential components of the required service ecosystem (such as the EUDAT license tool¹⁴).

As part of this deliverable, we updated the provisional Data Management Plan for the DiSSCo Infrastructure by:

1. Transferring and updating the textual content of the traditional DMP into a GitHub repository.
2. Implementing the RDA's Common Standard for maDMPs with new functionalities to enhance the machine-actionability of the DiSSCo DMP on the PlutoF platform.

¹² <https://plutof.docs.apiary.io/>

¹³ <https://support.datacite.org/docs/api>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/ufal/public-license-selector>

By moving the traditional DMP into a GitHub repository, users gain access to a more dynamic, digital format that is easier to maintain and modify. This eliminates the need for manual updates and sharing drafts between contributors, ensuring that users always work with the most current and accurate version of the DMP.

The integration of the maDMP into the traditional DMP of the DiSSCo infrastructure enhances usability for DiSSCo users by:

1. Streamlining the process of managing, updating, and accessing data management information.
2. Standardising data input, making it interoperable with other tools and repositories through web services.
3. Providing additional features such as metadata prefill, dynamic updates, and seamless publishing via DataCite, which— through a user-friendly interface—reduces administrative workload and improves reporting options. Additionally, improved data discoverability and citation tracking enhance the visibility and impact of research outputs.

Ultimately, the integration of maDMP improves the overall efficiency and quality of the data management processes, supporting long-term sustainability and compliance with international data-sharing standards.

5. References

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